

Table S1. Combination of redocking parameters to validate the docking protocol using GOLD.

GA runs	Fix all protein rotatable bonds	Configuration template	Scoring function	Size (Å)	Solution (Soln: no.)	RMSD (Å)
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:8	2.0241
					Soln:6	2.0542
					Soln:4	2.3641
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:15	1.4913
					Soln:13	1.5581
					Soln:6	1.8046
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:6	1.4433
					Soln:38	1.7407
					Soln:60	1.7734
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:21	1.0174
					Soln:88	1.0273
					Soln:5	1.2902
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:1	1.1492
					Soln:2	5.7927
					Soln:7	7.7993
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:10	1.0084
					Soln:2	1.5061
					Soln:20	2.1583
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:40	0.9904
					Soln:10	1.0084
					Soln:62	1.0782
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:17	0.8783
					Soln:189	0.9732
					Soln:110	0.9739
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:6	2.1420
					Soln:8	2.2288
					Soln:7	2.2817
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:13	1.7370
					Soln:14	1.9831
					Soln:15	2.0212
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:40	0.9904
					Soln:10	1.0084
					Soln:62	1.0782
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:65	1.1860
					Soln:47	1.4891
					Soln:81	1.5101
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:7	1.5150
					Soln:1	2.0580
					Soln:5	2.0618
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:1	1.1510

					Soln:7	1.5150
					Soln:15	1.8000
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:1	1.1510
					Soln:69	1.4331
					Soln:56	1.4881
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:146	0.8867
					Soln:106	0.9832
					Soln:1	1.1510
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:1	1.1492
					Soln:2	5.7927
					Soln:7	7.7993
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:11	1.4937
					Soln:2	1.5651
					Soln:3	1.9787
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:69	0.9503
					Soln:5	1.2632
					Soln:23	1.4372
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:69	0.9503
					Soln:144	1.1901
					Soln:5	1.2632
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:6	2.1420
					Soln:8	2.2288
					Soln:7	2.2817
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:3	2.2074
					Soln:9	2.2725
					Soln:16	2.2851
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:75	1.6993
					Soln:92	1.7394
					Soln:45	1.7563
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:112	1.1499
					Soln:114	1.5811
					Soln:75	1.6993
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:10	1.8444
					Soln:1	2.3047
					Soln:8	3.7787
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:14	1.8169
					Soln:10	1.8444
					Soln:9	1.9143
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:95	1.4264
					Soln:2	1.5337
					Soln:81	1.6202
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:87	1.2318
					Soln:56	1.2877

					Soln:159	1.3204
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:5	2.3828
					Soln:2	4.3757
					Soln:4	5.3104
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:4	1.4928
					Soln:3	1.8802
					Soln:5	2.3828
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:10	1.2584
					Soln:4	1.4928
					Soln:44	1.6935
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:87	1.1254
					Soln:10	1.2584
					Soln:165	1.3269
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:4	1.9306
					Soln:8	2.1346
					Soln:1	2.2211
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln: 17	1.7278
					Soln:19	1.9208
					Soln:4	1.9306
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:22	1.6535
					Soln:17	1.7278
					Soln:89	1.8730
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:178	1.0576
					Soln:120	1.3616
					Soln:113	1.6527
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:9	1.8168
					Soln:2	1.9390
					Soln:7	1.9504
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:15	1.5393
					Soln:3	1.7686
					Soln:9	1.8168
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:99	0.9176
					Soln:26	1.3467
					Soln:71	1.4676
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:99	0.9176
					Soln:53	1.0333
					Soln:33	1.1164
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:7	2.2265
					Soln:5	5.4966
					Soln:9	5.9109
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:11	1.9973
					Soln:12	2.1522
					Soln:7	2.2265

100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:13	0.9053
					Soln:17	0.9563
					Soln:21	1.2166
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:13	0.9053
					Soln:17	0.9563
					Soln:126	1.0896
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:9	1.9941
					Soln:8	2.1564
					Soln:2	2.3021
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:5	2.0321
					Soln:9	2.0334
					Soln:19	2.2890
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:16	1.0060
					Soln:87	1.8548
					Soln:35	1.9934
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:16	1.0060
					Soln:87	1.8548
					Soln:140	1.9126
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:5	1.6250
					Soln:4	2.0503
					Soln:1	2.3149
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:6	1.6310
					Soln:7	1.6794
					Soln:3	2.4074
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:93	1.1387
					Soln:98	1.3373
					Soln:30	1.4151
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:187	1.1770
					Soln:40	1.4511
					Soln:181	1.4873
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:7	5.0474
					Soln:4	5.2950
					Soln:8	5.4061
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:5	2.2899
					Soln:7	5.0474
					Soln:4	5.2950
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:8	1.7790
					Soln:54	1.8374
					Soln:72	1.9380
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:73	1.1270
					Soln:102	1.2204
					Soln:72	1.2736
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:5	2.1486

					Soln:3	2.2554
					Soln:8	2.3017
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:10	1.9021
					Soln:5	2.1486
					Soln:18	2.2227
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:23	1.8392
					Soln:71	1.8684
					Soln:10	1.9021
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:162	1.3340
					Soln:23	1.8392
					Soln:71	1.8684
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:9	1.8269
					Soln:3	2.0680
					Soln:10	3.8342
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:4	1.4253
					Soln:9	1.6118
					Soln:3	1.7423
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:37	1.1024
					Soln:13	1.1568
					Soln:59	1.2907
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:96	0.8632
					Soln:37	1.1024
					Soln:13	1.1568
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:3	2.1682
					Soln:1	5.9724
					Soln:7	6.1673
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:3	2.1682
					Soln:11	2.5261
					Soln:9	5.4613
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:47	1.2611
					Soln:65	1.3508
					Soln:51	1.3574
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:84	0.8280
					Soln:3	1.0165
					Soln:47	1.2611
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:3	2.3201
					Soln:8	2.3505
					Soln:2	2.3587
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:10	1.9377
					Soln:18	2.1846
					Soln:7	2.3109
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:88	1.9072
					Soln:10	1.9377

					Soln:48	1.9722
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:58	1.7939
					Soln:88	1.9072
					Soln:161	1.9081
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:10	2.1316
					Soln:8	2.4736
					Soln:6	4.2979
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:10	2.1316
					Soln:11	2.2876
					Soln:8	2.4736
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:34	1.3361
					Soln:17	1.7639
					Soln:45	1.8624
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:25	1.2883
					Soln:34	1.3361
					Soln:179	1.6470
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:5	5.5084
					Soln:1	5.8074
					Soln:9	5.8090
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:19	1.5332
					Soln:7	2.2654
					Soln:16	5.2340
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:76	1.1020
					Soln:19	1.5332
					Soln:8	1.8270
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:76	1.1020
					Soln:185	1.1102
					Soln:19	1.5332
10	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	2.0118
					Soln:1	2.2968
					Soln:2	4.0936
20	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	2.0118
					Soln:14	2.0508
					Soln:12	2.1124
100	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:2	1.0238
					Soln:49	1.3726
					Soln:66	1.5656
200	Yes	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:2	1.0238
					Soln:191	1.2858
					Soln:49	1.3726
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:2	2.1359
					Soln:9	4.2787
					Soln:8	4.3044

20	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:9	1.1584
					Soln:10	1.6642
					Soln:18	1.6830
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:9	1.1584
					Soln:63	1.3301
					Soln:77	1.5966
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:9	1.1584
					Soln:63	1.3301
					Soln:69	1.3769
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:9	5.3830
					Soln:4	5.4878
					Soln:5	5.6646
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:12	2.1598
					Soln:7	2.2871
					Soln:16	5.3736
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:12	2.1598
					Soln:7	2.2871
					Soln:79	2.3403
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:127	1.1158
					Soln:17	1.2966
					Soln:111	1.9803
10	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	3.4926
					Soln:10	8.6562
					Soln:4	8.7078
20	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:18	1.9391
					Soln:9	2.2535
					Soln:16	2.3169
100	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:17	1.1280
					Soln:55	1.1824
					Soln:49	1.4092
200	Yes	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:193	1.0352
					Soln:17	1.1280
					Soln:136	1.1456
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:8	1.8689
					Soln:2	2.0583
					Soln:10	5.3321
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:18	1.8618
					Soln:8	1.8689
					Soln:2	2.0583
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:49	1.4788
					Soln:58	1.5185
					Soln:46	1.5422
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:134	1.3370

					Soln:49	1.4788
					Soln:86	1.4952
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:5	5.1954
					Soln:8	5.7109
					Soln:6	5.9642
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:10	5.0307
					Soln:5	5.1954
					Soln:3	5.1968
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:53	1.0320
					Soln:52	1.8656
					Soln:88	1.9504
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:53	1.0320
					Soln:104	1.2107
					Soln:31	1.5728
10	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:6	1.5342
					Soln:9	1.9076
					Soln:7	2.0064
20	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:6	1.5342
					Soln:9	1.9076
					Soln:3	1.9297
100	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:90	0.9453
					Soln:40	1.2993
					Soln:12	1.4737
200	Yes	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:90	0.9453
					Soln:197	1.1655
					Soln:40	1.2993
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:5	1.5260
					Soln:6	1.9884
					Soln:1	4.3438
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:20	1.3104
					Soln:5	1.5260
					Soln:19	1.7939
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:20	1.3104
					Soln:23	1.4501
					Soln:19	1.4905
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:20	1.3104
					Soln:164	1.3579
					Soln:23	1.4501
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:6	2.7149
					Soln:5	7.0569
					Soln:7	7.1450
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:7	1.7020
					Soln:5	1.7151

					Soln:10	2.0128
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:92	1.3100
					Soln:10	1.5372
					Soln:7	1.7020
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:182	1.2437
					Soln:92	1.3100
					Soln:129	1.5160
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:1	1.7690
					Soln:9	1.7691
					Soln:4	2.0786
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:15	1.5279
					Soln:1	1.7690
					Soln:9	1.7691
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:14	1.3484
					Soln:64	1.4910
					Soln:15	1.5279
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:139	1.0859
					Soln:126	1.1841
					Soln:14	1.3184
10	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:1	1.9326
					Soln:8	2.0673
					Soln:7	2.6466
20	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:14	1.4561
					Soln:19	1.8674
					Soln:1	1.9326
100	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:67	1.1116
					Soln:8	1.2544
					Soln:2	1.2822
200	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:194	0.9288
					Soln:67	1.1116
					Soln:8	1.2544
10	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:10	5.0577
					Soln:8	5.4453
					Soln:6	5.5164
20	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:6	1.9693
					Soln:8	2.2319
					Soln:9	2.6602
100	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:61	1.0885
					Soln:63	1.3479
					Soln:42	1.5032
200	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	6	Soln:61	1.0885
					Soln:141	1.2846
					Soln:63	1.3479

10	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:4	2.1536
					Soln:1	2.2143
					Soln:5	2.3229
20	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:18	1.2424
					Soln:13	1.9465
					Soln:6	2.0920
100	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:18	1.2424
					Soln:80	1.3268
					Soln:53	1.6671
200	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	6	Soln:18	1.2424
					Soln:80	1.3268
					Soln:6	1.5787
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:9	1.1969
					Soln:1	1.4427
					Soln:6	2.3743
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:9	1.1969
					Soln:1	1.4427
					Soln:6	1.5757
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:4	0.9909
					Soln:9	1.1969
					Soln:19	1.3609
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	6	Soln:4	0.9909
					Soln:9	1.1969
					Soln:101	1.2182
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:8	1.2413
					Soln:5	1.5544
					Soln:1	2.3914
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:18	0.8680
					Soln:16	1.1118
					Soln:8	1.2413
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:18	0.8680
					Soln:16	1.1118
					Soln:8	1.2413
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	6	Soln:18	0.8680
					Soln:16	1.1118
					Soln:8	1.2413
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:10	1.9512
					Soln:3	2.0501
					Soln:5	2.3346
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:6	1.7767
					Soln:20	1.8305
					Soln:10	1.8607
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:81	1.1030

					Soln:23	1.5961
					Soln:19	1.6713
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	6	Soln:81	1.1030
					Soln:149	1.1771
					Soln:47	1.2376
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:5	1.8917
					Soln:9	2.0267
					Soln:8	3.5521
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:3	1.7202
					Soln:8	1.8451
					Soln:10	1.8573
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:76	1.1783
					Soln:91	1.2409
					Soln:87	1.2499
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:199	1.0373
					Soln:76	1.1783
					Soln:91	1.2409
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:8	1.5280
					Soln:6	5.6637
					Soln:7	5.8002
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:8	1.5280
					Soln:2	2.3010
					Soln:17	2.3738
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:47	1.3321
					Soln:64	1.5195
					Soln:8	1.5280
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:47	1.3321
					Soln:124	1.4647
					Soln:64	1.5195
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:3	2.0541
					Soln:6	2.2493
					Soln:1	8.6164
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:3	2.0541
					Soln:6	2.2493
					Soln:7	2.2994
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:23	1.7675
					Soln:13	1.7984
					Soln:1	1.8781
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:2	1.5069
					Soln:33	1.5827
					Soln:11	1.6112
10	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:8	1.0837
					Soln:5	1.6286

					Soln:4	2.0319
20	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:8	1.0837
					Soln:3	1.5241
					Soln:5	1.6286
100	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:8	1.0837
					Soln:23	1.2186
					Soln:4	1.2736
200	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:189	1.0536
					Soln:8	1.0837
					Soln:23	1.2186
10	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:10	2.0013
					Soln:3	2.1874
					Soln:7	2.7278
20	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:14	1.5765
					Soln:10	2.0013
					Soln:3	2.1874
100	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:92	1.3732
					Soln:14	1.5765
					Soln:57	1.6243
200	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	10	Soln:143	1.2091
					Soln:92	1.3732
					Soln:14	1.5765
10	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:8	2.1879
					Soln:2	2.2771
					Soln:7	2.4063
20	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:4	1.8543
					Soln:2	1.9653
					Soln:9	2.0984
100	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:73	1.4644
					Soln:25	1.5227
					Soln:8	1.5752
200	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	10	Soln:105	1.4588
					Soln:76	1.4644
					Soln:25	1.5227
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:2	1.1198
					Soln:3	1.2068
					Soln:4	1.7064
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:2	1.1198
					Soln:3	1.2068
					Soln:13	1.6723
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:2	1.1198
					Soln:3	1.2068
					Soln:37	1.3051

200	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	10	Soln:67	0.8777
					Soln:2	1.1198
					Soln:35	1.1500
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:10	5.7606
					Soln:7	5.8738
					Soln:2	6.6045
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:8	1.9133
					Soln:11	5.7336
					Soln:10	5.7606
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:63	1.7809
					Soln:8	1.9133
					Soln:83	1.9887
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	10	Soln:45	1.3763
					Soln:89	1.4343
					Soln:78	1.4391
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:10	2.2926
					Soln:7	2.3204
					Soln:1	3.5918
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:15	2.0385
					Soln:12	2.1370
					Soln:17	2.1424
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:64	1.5552
					Soln:55	1.7149
					Soln:40	1.8153
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	10	Soln:163	1.1630
					Soln:64	1.5552
					Soln:86	1.5932
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:1	2.2561
					Soln:5	4.0120
					Soln:9	4.1754
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:1	2.2561
					Soln:15	2.4917
					Soln:2	3.9382
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:23	1.3280
					Soln:60	1.5914
					Soln:51	2.0234
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:49	1.2780
					Soln:23	1.3280
					Soln:48	1.5215
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:1	2.2838
					Soln:2	4.2151
					Soln:9	4.3677
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:1	2.2838

					Soln:9	2.5048
					Soln:16	2.7661
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:1	1.3533
					Soln:46	1.4587
					Soln:64	1.9397
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:1	1.3533
					Soln:40	1.4396
					Soln:46	1.4587
10	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:5	2.4742
					Soln:4	2.8812
					Soln:9	6.9543
20	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:8	1.6330
					Soln:20	1.9241
					Soln:4	2.0178
100	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:1	1.5278
					Soln:8	1.6330
					Soln:87	1.9170
200	No	Chemscore_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:75	0.9826
					Soln:68	1.2393
					Soln:185	1.2696
10	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:10	1.6870
					Soln:4	2.3614
					Soln:8	2.6194
20	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:10	1.6870
					Soln:9	2.0425
					Soln:4	2.2682
100	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:61	1.6824
					Soln:10	1.6870
					Soln:44	1.7172
200	No	Gold_kinase	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:174	1.1087
					Soln:100	1.2669
					Soln:68	1.5471
10	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:4	5.7160
					Soln:2	5.8796
					Soln:10	6.1206
20	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:8	2.6425
					Soln:13	4.9880
					Soln:9	5.5335
100	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:96	2.6065
					Soln:57	2.3716
					Soln:8	2.6425
200	No	Gold_kinase	ChemScore	20	Soln:143	1.4295
					Soln:87	1.7738

					Soln:96	1.8293
10	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	1.7354
					Soln:1	2.3751
					Soln:2	2.5736
20	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	1.7354
					Soln:10	2.1571
					Soln:17	2.3008
100	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:32	1.7201
					Soln:7	1.7354
					Soln:66	1.9503
200	No	Gold_kinase	GoldScore	20	Soln:177	1.2033
					Soln:121	1.4774
					Soln:122	1.4921
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:7	2.0944
					Soln:5	3.6109
					Soln:10	3.8141
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:7	2.0944
					Soln:19	2.2847
					Soln:5	3.6109
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:54	1.6388
					Soln:48	1.7669
					Soln:28	1.7705
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	CHEMPLP	20	Soln:59	1.3246
					Soln:109	1.7782
					Soln:20	1.8284
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:2	5.4456
					Soln:7	5.8176
					Soln:6	5.9547
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:9	3.1765
					Soln:2	5.4456
					Soln:6	5.5397
100	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:11	1.5251
					Soln:80	2.0522
					Soln:89	2.2072
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	ChemScore	20	Soln:143	1.1905
					Soln:11	1.5251
					Soln:89	1.5814
10	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:7	2.1880
					Soln:6	2.2271
					Soln:3	2.3261
20	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:10	2.0068
					Soln:5	2.0693
					Soln:3	2.1837

100	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:44	1.2940
					Soln:80	1.4807
					Soln:64	1.4888
200	No	Gold_serine_protease	GoldScore	20	Soln:74	1.2751
					Soln:44	1.2940
					Soln:147	1.3351